

A Privacy-Preserving Attention-Driven Deep Learning Framework for Intelligent Intrusion Detection in Secure Cloud and Smart Computing Environments

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Abstract--Cloud computing and smart environments are increasingly targeted by sophisticated cyber-attacks, making secure and intelligent intrusion detection systems critical for maintaining data integrity and privacy. Traditional security solutions often struggle with high-dimensional traffic data, imbalanced classes, and limited interpretability. To address these challenges, this research proposes an AI-Based Intelligent Data Analysis framework for secure cloud and smart computing systems. The framework employs the UNSW-NB15 dataset, which undergoes comprehensive preprocessing, including cleaning, categorical encoding, class balancing, and Z-score normalization, followed by dimensionality reduction using PCA. A privacy-preserving layer integrating AES-256 encryption, JWT authentication, and secure key management ensures secure storage and controlled access within a private cloud simulation. Deep Autoencoders and Variational Autoencoders extract latent features and detect anomalies, while an Attention-Enhanced Deep Neural Network performs multi-class attack classification. Ensemble decision-making with probabilistic risk assessment generates prioritized alerts, and SHAP-based Explainable AI provides feature-level interpretability. Experimental results demonstrate high accuracy, robust detection of low- and high-risk threats, minimal false positives, and near-perfect ROC-AUC (0.9971), outperforming other advanced models.

Keywords--AI-based intrusion detection, Secure cloud computing, Attention-enhanced deep learning, Variational autoencoder and Explainable AI.

I. INTRODUCTION

The adoption of cloud computing and smart computing systems has altered the current IT infrastructures rapidly, where organizations are now able to store, process, and exchange a large quantity of data in an efficient way [1]. Cloud environments offer the scalable resources and flexible models of deployment and smart computing incorporates IoT devices, edge computing, and real-time analytics to provide efficiency in operations in areas of healthcare, finance, and manufacturing [2]. Nonetheless, this enhanced connectivity and dependence on electronic mediums has also brought onboard an expanding list of cybersecurity risks to systems, such as malware, ransomware, denial-of-service (DoS), and zero-day exploits [3]. They might steal sensitive information, interfere with important functions and cause significant financial and reputation losses [4]. The conventional intrusion detection systems (IDS) and security efforts have a hard time

dealing with the present day cyber threats [5]. Traditional methods usually use signature detection or predefined rule set which finds it difficult to detect new attacks or adjust to a changing threat environment. The effectiveness of these systems is further decreased by high-dimensional network traffic data, imbalance of classes between normal and malicious records and sheer amount of traffic. Also, a great number of currently available AI-based procedures cannot be interpreted, and security analysts may not trust or authenticate automated decision making, especially in regulatory compliance and forensic investigations [6]. In order to address these shortcomings, AI-Based Intelligent Data Analysis has become a potential solution to secure cloud computing and intelligent computing systems. It is based on the idea that deep learning models such as autoencoders and variational autoencoders can be trained to learn useful and small representations of network traffic and to identify anomalies by reconstructing the input and using probabilistic modeling to detect the presence of anomalies.

A. Key contribution

An overall end-to-end intelligent system is proposed for secure cloud and intelligent computing setting, which involves data preprocessing, privacy preservation, deep learning-based threat detection, risk assessment, and explainability in single architecture.

The model is a hybrid of deterministic latent feature learning (Deep Autoencoder) and probabilistic modeling (VAE) with a goal of improving the detection of unknown and zero-day attacks by reconstruction error and distribution-based anomaly scoring.

An Attention-DNN model is dynamically assigned as giving priority to security-relevant features to enhance the detection error, false positive rate, and minority class recognition in the multi-class intrusion detection cases.

An innovative ensemble decision model combines the probability of anomalies and the level of classification performance, and then creates prioritized levels of threats and automated notifications through probabilistic risk evaluation (Risk = Probability \times Impact).

The AES-256 encryption, JWT-authentication, Role-Based Access Control (RBAC), and secure RESTful APIs have been integrated into the system to guarantee confidentiality, integrity, and authorized access to data in private clouds.

The framework improves interpretability because it explains model decisions both globally and locally, which facilitates trust of analysts, forensic analysis, and regulatory compliance.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Recent researches point to a major advancement in AI-centred cloud security frameworks. To obtain high accuracy with high computational cost and scalability problems, Vijay Kumar Gandam and Aravind [7] suggested a deep learning intrusion detection model that incorporates Morlet Wavelet Kernel, MLSTM, and JBOA to provide optimal feature selection. Wa'ad H. Aljuaid and Sultan S. Alshamrani [8] created a CNN-based IDS which was tested on CSE-CIC-IDS2018 with over 98% accuracy but had overfitting and the constraint of real time deployment. Sanyam Jain [9] proposed an AI-based threat detection system based on behavioral analytics and predictive modeling to enhance proactive security but needs maintain retraining and maintaining high infrastructure. Aswa [10] used CNN, RNN, and Transformer models with (real-time) and zero-day detection on CICIDS2017 and NSL-KDD, but at a high cost and with lower explainability. Moreover, Dr. Abdinasir Ismael Hashi and Abdirizak Mohamed Hashi [11] proposed deep learning cloud edge architecture with a Secure Unified Data Model that makes the system more resilient but more complex and difficult to implement. Generally, the previous studies have a high detection rate but have difficulties in scaling, efficiency, privacy maintenance, interpretability and application in real-time.

A. Research gaps

The current AI-driven cloud security systems primarily focus on the accuracy of detection but ignore the computational efficiency, scalability, and the ability to deploy the system in real-time. They tend to have a high degree of complexity, consumption of more resources and poor management of unbalanced data and zero-day attacks. Additionally, resilience to adversarial attacks, excellent data confidentiality protocols, and the ability to explain decisions are not well covered and thus, highlight the requirement of a lightweight, scalable, privacy-conscious, and interpretable intrusion detection system.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed methodology develops a privacy preserving and secure AI-based intrusion detection framework on cloud and smart computing environments using UNSW-NB15 dataset. The first step is data preprocessing, which involves data cleaning, categorical encoding, imbalance between the classes, and Z-score normalization to enhance efficiency and the second is dimensionality reduction, which is achieved through PCA. A privacy protecting layer incorporates the AES-256 encryption, JWT-based authentication and secure management of keys prior to implementation in a confidential cloud with RBAC and secure RESTful APIs. Deep Autoencoders and Variational Autoencoders are used in extracting latent features, detecting anomalies, and an Attention-Enhanced Deep Neural Network is used in multi-class attack classification. The system also uses ensemble decision-making and probabilistic risk evaluation of

prioritized detection of threats and automated notifications, and Explainable AI with SHAP gives transparency and interpretability of model decisions. The proposed methodology architecture is presented in fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Architecture for the proposed methodology

A. Input collection from UNSW-NB15 dataset

The input data is collected from the UNSW-NB15, created in 2015 by the Cyber Range Lab at the Australian Centre for Cyber Security and that is publicly accessible at Kaggle. It holds realistic network traffic produced with IXIA PerfectStorm tool, such as benign and malicious records. This dataset is composed of 49 flow-, content-, and time-based features where there are labels of normal traffic and nine attack types. Having more than 2.5 million records that are separated into training and testing sets, it is extensive as a benchmark in AI-based intrusion detection in secure cloud environments. Let the dataset be defined as:

$$D = \{ (X_i, Y_i) \}_{i=1}^N \quad (1)$$

Where: X_i = Feature vector of network record I, Y_i = Class label (Normal or Attack category) and N = Total number of records.

B. Data Preprocessing

Once the input of the UNSW-NB15 dataset is gathered, a structured preprocessing step is performed and helps to improve the quality of data and increase the effectiveness of the models. The first step is that, there are 82,332 rows and 45 columns in the dataset which capture different features of network traffic. Missing, null and inconsistent values are also detected during preprocessing and the values are correctly dealt with to maintain the integrity of the data. Categorical values like protocol type, service and connection state are encoded into numeric format through the relevant encoding techniques, which rendered them suitable to machine learning algorithms. Random under-

sampling is used to balance the classes to eliminate dominance in the majority and to achieve a balanced dataset of 74000 rows and 45 columns, to deal with class imbalance between normal and attack records. Lastly, Z-score normalization is done to normalize numerical features whereby the mean is zero and the standard deviation is one. All the numerical characteristics are standardized with:

$$Z = \frac{X - \mu}{\sigma} \quad (2)$$

Where: X = Original feature value, μ = Mean of the feature and σ = Standard deviation. This makes all the features to be on an equal scale and avoids a domination of large-value features. To handle imbalance:

$$D_{balanced} = D_{normal}^k \cup D_{attack}^k \quad (3)$$

Where: k = Equal number of samples selected from each class. This guarantees equal learning and reduces the model bias.

TABLE I. PREPROCESSED AND BALANCED UNSW-NB15 DATASET SAMPLE

4	23282	0.000009	117	2	4	2	0	114	0
0		rate	...	ct_dst_sport_ltm	ct_dst_src_ltm	is_ftp_logIn	\		
0		216.274948	...	1	3	0			
1		0.000000	...	1	1	0			
2		1000000.002500	...	1	39	0			
3		197.326610	...	1	2	0			
4		111111.107200	...	25	26	0			
0		ct_ftp_cmd	ct_flw_http_mthd	ct_src_ltm	ct_srv_dst	is_sm_ips_ports	\		
0		0	0	3	7	0			
1		0	0	1	1	1			
2		0	0	14	39	0			
3		0	0	2	1	0			
4		0	0	25	26	0			
		attack_cat	label						
0		0	0						
1		0	0						
2		3	1						
3		0	0						
4		1	1						

Table 1 is the preprocessed UNSW-NB15 dataset with data cleaning, categorical encoding and class balancing. It contains the required network traffic characteristics of duration, protocol, service, state, count of packets and bytes, traffic rate, connection based statistical properties, attack type and binary class labels. Random under-sampling helps in obtaining balanced representation of both normal and attack and reduces model biases and offers a structured and clean dataset to be further analyzed and model development.

C. Feature Extraction

PCA is used in the dimensionality reduction after preprocessing. The original 43 input features are reduced to 16 uncorrelated principal components that capture about 95.10% of all the variance. This guarantees minimum loss of information and at the same time ensures a significant reduction in the complexity of computation. The smaller feature space is better at increasing the speed of training, reducing memory, decreasing overfitting, and making the resulting learning models more efficient and productive.

$$X_{pca} = XW \quad (4)$$

Where: X = Original feature matrix, W = Projection matrix (principal components) and X_{pca} = Reduced feature matrix.

Explained variance:

$$EV = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_j} \quad (5)$$

Where: λ_j = Eigenvalues, m = Selected components, n = Original components. This saves computational time and at the same time, it does not lose valuable details.

D. Privacy-Preserving Data Security Layer

Once features have been extracted, Privacy-Preserving Data Security Layer will be added to secure sensitive network data prior to the use of the cloud. It employs a hybrid encryption strategy in which Advanced Encryption Standard (AES-256) is implemented to guarantee a high level of confidentiality when storing and transmitting the data, and token-based authentication with the help of JSON Web Token (JWT) is applied to allow only authorized users to access the information. The management of keys is also required to be protected in order to stop compromise of keys. These mechanisms together guarantee the data confidentiality, integrity and limited accessibility in cloud-based AI systems. Prior to the deployment of the cloud:

1) AES-256 Encryption

$$C = E(K, P) \quad (6)$$

$$P = D(K, C) \quad (7)$$

Where: P = Plaintext data, C = Ciphertext, K = Encryption key, E = Encryption function and D = Decryption function. This provides confidentiality when storing and transmitting.

2) JWT Authentication

Token generation:

$$Token = Encode(Header, Payload, Secret) \quad (8)$$

This ensures only authorized users can access cloud data.

TABLE II. ENCRYPTION AND DECRYPTION PROCESS USING

```
Original: b'{"feature1":10,"feature2":25,"feature3":100}'
Encrypted: b'gAAAAABjCidqpf155560NdykCvMkdt-1j3uyfdlmmPZY48XCu44LO-OS_13720V66883grPhmksuk69770rk_jateBF-KEC3i5qic3j3108MNIIVf-clp1L2xxkLzHPHE_a0'
```

AES-256

Table 2 depicts the encryption process of AES-256 in the privacy-preserving security layer and the process has three stages, which include original feature data (plaintext), encrypted ciphertext, and the successful decrypted output. After transforming the feature values into plaintext, they are encrypted into inaccessible ciphertext to make sure that, in case of cloud storage or transmission, the information is not read by anyone and finally a secure key is used to decrypt the ciphertext causing the original data to be correctly restored.

This confirms the trustworthiness, truthfulness and reliable recovery of the encryption framework.

E. Secure Cloud Data Management (Private Cloud Simulation)

A private cloud simulation is constructed after deploying the privacy-preserving layer to have a secure Data Management framework of data deployment and data operations. The encrypted information is safely stored and operated under RBAC where the permission and accountability are strictly controlled by predefined roles like Admin, Security Analyst and User. RESTful APIs that are secured using HTTPS provide an option to communicate encrypted messages and authenticate access between the cloud modules. These mechanisms along with each other will guarantee controlled access, secure data sharing, and effective integration of AI-based threat detection into the cloud environment.

Role-Based Access Control ensures controlled access:

$$Access = f(UserRole, Permission) \quad (9)$$

Where: User Role \in {Admin, Analyst, User}, Permission = Allowed operations. Only authorized roles can decrypt and access protected data.

TABLE III. ENCRYPTED DATA STORAGE IN PRIVATE CLOUD ENVIRONMENT

```
gAAAAABjCmarvdJWXI7EejZ206RLoRBH-lvTsvLOYs_dDumTeRfc2ObBuYQ4e2b-lMw-
ILX4HmYKePc_Dk01MwVbOMz2coEUvoNsmsoFFNinfszW8LxhyBj-
Vzq2j_shjySelaBhab4WsbvrbOASWYqQFpkW3ekK0BEj4KNsGYfK4thlRzc_8Ay6M-Kg92-
9y/Hlnc4B0n0k7BNA_IB_IL829B2HWg3XDLKadPzRajALpHpFjilv29lme6KlhpwF_gAaO9ivG1q9yHmScao13L7D12Rc4Tbr
b7RFZhgAsApuDyU1u5pDRsSbspSQHtIbFO8s5ugHT_OFREIL28eNPP-
afGI8d6DFPeeymiK_nidGHjr3Vgt0BPhyW9OwVZisvOIF9BtdidRMAb4LC-SR-
k53mjVCinta75flGCrkD35dpiQYMa3OZxcagePbQyoniNFlwUoAOBkKQVRVXq0ITAMjgEJ39hsT_45K3SEcaiq117aCk5dD
ayWA3mwwk80o_4Np7fouWXRkZzOeJ4U8S16lMQ_Sqjwvxy69pPlq_lmBQyQw1l68Y7QhBJPDA0Y0HULbBADeaaA0C3k0
QCezUry2SDrD4XmJZFCNh2Tpn2yMCA4biresj_CsPihaw0oH8AjZEP5QhMCgMW1A2qVcf_gn1R0fC0z7Q8Ufco29TJ
wTBoxi4baA8ur9aKVLBcJ2uv9R8H9EtikLu16ANF1FNORJlUZpcegn6_J1Wu4H7KLIIFs0fWEn3fj2Z2X05cQ0Vb_6broLEXT
o9ZQffPzw1lH8_1lkDOEYxSDh8vNesm-p5sobvtr98DFt2gt5EYWyKTL8q-
3HqR0Fria6BTN1cXaYPVoZhCmVxWmPwup2p4v0qpnZQWMI2ovZ9tLbpGpJvMxOyRfKcytX1dGDILyClwfbRzSvWw
orcWkZsyJVL_DJc3_P_RpdB2i6BAGzJ3_w0LlAW-
NW0wB0LGMENhH45vkcA4n6JxHWpZpxl7k8TRWdoayRZCgT42D3r2LF-w==
gAAAAABjCmalheOKf465_mivniVqjHddi-5bul5hh_OdSHfcl-
```

Table 3 displays the encrypted table of the processed dataset that has been stored in the private cloud environment. The original content of features is encrypted using AES-256 transformed into incomplete readable ciphertext, which is subsequently stored or transferred thus being secure against unauthorized use. The effectiveness and reliability of the privacy-preserving cloud storage mechanism is supported by the encryption confirmation of the entire set of data (74,000 × 43 features).

TABLE IV. SECURE DATA ACCESS AND DECRYPTION VERIFICATION

```
✓ Key loaded successfully
Data to encrypt shape: (74000, 43)
✓ data encrypted and securely stored
✓ Secure data accessed successfully
Decrypted data shape: (74000, 43)
```

id	dur	proto	service	state	spkts	dstkts	dstbytes	rate	...	ct_dst_tm	ct_src_dport_tm	ct_dst_sport_tm	ct_dst_src_tm	isftp_login
0	37564.0	0.198821	111.0	0.0	3.0	22.0	4768.0	2664.0	...	10.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	3.0
1	73720.0	0.000000	6.0	0.0	4.0	1.0	0.0	0.000000	...	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
2	3945.0	0.000010	117.0	0.0	4.0	2.0	0.0	1372.0	...	14.0	14.0	1.0	39.0	0.0
3	28604.0	0.663874	111.0	1.0	3.0	72.0	60.0	12576.0	...	2.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	0.0
4	23282.0	0.000009	117.0	2.0	4.0	2.0	0.0	114.0	...	25.0	25.0	25.0	26.0	0.0

5 rows × 43 columns

Table 4 affirms the retrieval and decryption of the encrypted data in the private cloud setting. Following a safe

authentication using RBAC and RESTful API, the data is decrypted and reconstructed into its initial structured format (74,000 × 43), and a sample (5 × 43) is shown to verification. System messages ensure that all data integrity, security, and reliability are assured during the encryption, storage, access, and decryption of the data.

Fig. 2. Secure Cloud Data Access Workflow with Encryption and Token Verification

The secure cloud data access architecture (Figure 2) is used and encrypted data is stored safely on the cloud and is accessed via a layered protection system. The identity is checked by means of token-based authentication (e.g., JWT validation) to check user requests, and authorization is carried out before the secure decryption with encrypted cryptographic keys. Authorized users are only provided access which ensures confidentiality, controlled access and data integrity during the cloud data lifecycle.

F. AI-Driven Intelligent Data Analysis

The structure continues on the AI-Driven Intelligent Data Analysis layer, which carries out the central intelligence component that is able to identify the hidden patterns and the complex associations of the high-dimensional network traffic information. Deep representation learning is used in this step whereby meaningful and non-linear feature representations are automatically obtained based on the processed data. There are 43 features to begin with, which is reduced to a latent feature space of 16 dimensions with the help of a Deep Autoencoder as indicated. Dimensionality reduction helps in extracting the most informative features of the data and removes redundancy and noise at the same time. The Deep Autoencoder is a method that learns the compressed representations through a combination of encoding the input data to a lower-dimensional latent space followed by its reconstruction. In anomaly detection, reconstruction error is computed by the model, increased reconstruction error means that the patterns of normal traffic are not followed thus, suspicious or abnormal traffic is detected. A VAE also makes this process more effective, as it brings probabilistic modeling to the latent space and the system can learn about the underlying distribution of normal network behavior. This probabilistic method enhances the process of detecting an unknown or a zero-day attack by determining the cases that significantly do not conform to the learned distribution. Collectively, these deep learning methods allow intelligent, automatic identification of concealed patterns of attack and increase the threat detection power of the secure cloud framework.

TABLE V. DEEP AUTOENCODER LATENT FEATURE REPRESENTATION (43 → 16-DIMENSIONAL REDUCTION)

	AE_Feature_1	AE_Feature_2	AE_Feature_3	AE_Feature_4	AE_Feature_5	AE_Feature_6	AE_Feature_7	AE_Feature_8	AE_Feature_9	AE_Feature_10	AE_Feature_11	AE_Fo
0	-4.857794	2.094277	0.765266	0.360647	1.022429	-0.576929	1.012331	0.954318	0.259799	0.416292	-1.677607	-
1	1.732614	-5.997659	-4.506492	-1.663092	-6.920907	-8.815873	-0.231168	-6.813802	4.940419	7.301820	-7.229162	-
2	5.293988	-3.656839	-2.009131	0.810465	-5.072661	1.579332	3.540030	2.145363	0.492351	3.712148	-1.926314	-
3	-1.977371	0.997198	3.876962	1.263290	-2.110377	-2.822708	0.009498	0.447609	0.945496	-0.090662	-1.370960	-
4	4.644955	-0.806948	-0.915989	-0.833112	-3.202549	-0.898728	1.017805	-0.053353	-1.152676	1.262834	-0.602395	-

Table 5 reveals the compression of the latent feature space generated by Deep Autoencoder in which the number of original 43 input features is reduced to 16 latent features using the encoder network. These latent variables will include high-level, non-linear connections and obscure trends in the network traffic data. The encoded values (positive and negative) are the transformed low-dimensional representations that are to be used to analyze intelligent data with high efficiency.

G. Advanced Classification-Based Threat Detection

The extracted latent representations are sent to the Advanced Classification-Based Threat Detection layer after the Autoencoder + VAE phase of AI-Driven Intelligent Data Analysis. This layer will provide proper multi-class attack classification with the help of an Attention-Enhanced Deep Neural Network (Attention-DNN). The mechanism of operation of this layer is elaborated below.

1) Input Integration from Intelligent Analysis Layer

The classification module combines the latent features vectors which are compressed, reconstruction error scores based on autoencoders as well as probabilistic representations which are produced by the VAE and produces a joint high-level feature space. These inputs represent structural patterns, anomaly intensity and uncertainty traits of network traffic, respectively. The classifier can make better generalization, detect better and reduce the complexity of its computation on such abstractions because of noise reduction and information richness, which results in more efficient and reliable detection of threats in cloud environments.

2) Deep Neural Network Architecture

Deep neural network classifier consists of several fully connected dense layers that learn non-linear and complicated decision boundaries between normal and malicious network traffic. ReLU activation functions bring in non-linearity permitting the model to learn complex attack patterns but the use of batch normalization increases the stability of training and also improves the speed of convergence. The dropout layers are added to curb the overfitting through random deactivation of neurons during training. These elements, combined together, help to increasingly refine the input representations into abstractions of a higher level and thus accurately and robustly detect threats in dynamic cloud environments.

The Attention-DNN uses dense layers to learn non-linear decision boundaries:

$$H^l = \text{ReLU}(W^l F + b^l) \quad (10)$$

Where: H^l = Output of layer l , W^l, b^l = Weights and bias of layer l and ReLU = Non-linear activation

Dropout prevents overfitting:

$$H_{drop}^l = H^l \cdot \mathcal{I} \quad (11)$$

Where \mathcal{I} is a random mask for neuron deactivation.

Batch normalization stabilizes training:

$$H_{norm}^l = \frac{H^l - \mu}{\sigma} \quad (12)$$

Where μ, σ are the mean and standard deviation of the layer inputs.

3) Attention Mechanism Integration

The attention mechanism can be used to improve the deep neural network since it applies weighted importance to feature representations rather than treating them as equally important. All of the hidden features receive a learnable score that is normalized by a softmax function to produce attention weights. Such weights highlight the important security-related features and downplay the unimportant or noisy attributes, as well as, they lead to the representation of features in a weighted way. Such characteristics like

abnormal packet rates or abnormal connection states in cybersecurity cases are more effective indicators of attacks, the attention mechanism is designed to make those attributes more important in the ultimate classification decision, which leads to enhanced detection accuracy and the resistance to changing traffic patterns.

Attention assigns importance weights to features

$$\alpha_i = \frac{e^{s_i}}{\sum_j e^{s_j}}, Z' = \sum_i \alpha_i F_i \quad (13)$$

Where: S_i = Score for feature i , α_i = Attention weight and Z' = Weighted feature vector. This highlights such crucial security-related features as abnormal packet rates.

4) Multi-Class Classification Process

The attention weighted feature representation is fed into the last output layer where a probability distribution of several traffic classes is generated by a Softmax activation function. The model uses multi-classification to classify normal traffic and different types of attacks such as Fuzzers, DoS, Exploits, Reconnaissance, Shellcode, Backdoors, Worms, Analysis and Generic attacks. The most likely class is chosen as the final output, enabling precise and fine-grained identification of various cybersecurity threats in the cloud environment.

Final classification uses Softmax:

$$P(y=k) = \frac{e^{z_k}}{\sum_j e^{z_j}}, \hat{y} = \arg \max P(y=k)$$

(14) Where: Z_k = Logit for class k , $P(y=k)$ = Probability of class k and \hat{y} = Predicted attack class. The model is predictive of such classes as Fuzzers, DoS, Exploits, Reconnaissance, etc.

TABLE VI. ARCHITECTURE SUMMARY OF ATTENTION-ENHANCED DEEP NEURAL NETWORK FOR THREAT CLASSIFICATION

input_layer_2 (InputLayer)	(None, 1, 16)	0	-
multi_head_attention (MultiHeadAttention)	(None, 1, 16)	8,592	input_layer_2[0][0].input_layer_2[0][0]
layer_normalization (LayerNormalization)	(None, 1, 16)	32	multi_head_attention[0][0]
global_average_poolingid (GlobalAveragePoolingID)	(None, 16)	0	layer_normalization[0][0]
dense_10 (Dense)	(None, 64)	1,088	global_average_poolingid[-]
dropout_1 (Dropout)	(None, 64)	0	dense_10[0][0]
dense_11 (Dense)	(None, 32)	2,080	dropout_1[0][0]
dense_12 (Dense)	(None, 1)	33	dense_11[0][0]

Total params: 11,825 (46.19 KB)
Trainable params: 11,825 (46.19 KB)
Non-trainable params: 0 (0.00 B)

Table 6 gives a summary of proposed Attention-Enhanced Deep Neural Network (Attention-DNN) architecture of advanced threat classification. The input to the model is 16-dimensional latent features (74,000, 1, 16) and the output is the result of Multi-Head Attention layer to include inter-feature dependencies, followed by Layer Normalization and Global Average Pooling to represent features in a stable and compact way. The processed features go through Dropout and dense layers (64 and 32 neurons) to avoid overfitting and an end output layer to classify. The model has 11,825 trainable parameters and is computationally efficient as well as capable of learning intricate attack patterns to be practically deployed on the cloud.

H. Intelligent Decision and Alert System

The Intelligent Decision and Alert System transform the results of classification into security actions. It takes the scores of anomaly probability of the VAE module and multi-class prediction of the Attention-DNN through weighted ensemble to increase the robustness and minimize false positives. The threats are then divided into low, medium or high severity by a probabilistic risk assessment (Risk = Probability \times Impact). Depending on the risk level, events are captured, warning sent, or automatic responses are issued immediately, ensuring prioritized, efficient, and smart security management in the cloud environment.

Risk is computed as:

$$Risk = Probability \times Impact$$

(15) Where: Probability = Likelihood of attack (P_{final}) and Impact = Potential damage.

Threat levels:

$$ThreatLevel = \begin{cases} Low & Risk < T_1 \\ Medium & T_1 \leq Risk < T_2 \\ High & Risk \geq T_2 \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Alerts: Low: Logged, Medium: Warning and High: Immediate alert & automated response. This ensures prioritized response to critical threats.

TABLE VII. ENSEMBLE-BASED RISK SCORING AND THREAT LEVEL ALERT GENERATION SUMMARY

0	0	5.920631e-07	0.00	LOW	0
1	0	3.897145e-03	0.39	LOW	0
2	0	7.802444e-04	0.08	LOW	0
3	1	7.393135e-01	73.93	HIGH	1
4	1	1.000000e+00	100.00	CRITICAL	1

Table 7 gives the final result of Intelligent Decision and Alert System including True_Label, Attack_Probability (introduced by VAE and Attention-DNN ensemble), Risk_Score (Probability \times Impact) calculated, Threat level assigned, and Alert-Generated. Depending on preset thresholds, events are identified as LOW, MEDIUM, HIGH or CRITICAL with alerts only being raised in the high risk cases. Also signifies that 7338 alerts were created, and the majority of incidents was sorted as LOW risk and proves effective risk-based prioritization and focused security reaction in the safe cloud environment.

I. Explainable AI using SHAP

The framework combines an Explainable AI layer, based on SHAP, to improve transparency and interpretability of threat forecasts. SHAP measures the contribution of each feature based on grounds of game theory and offers both global explanations (the overall contribution of a feature to the entire dataset) and local explanations (the contribution of a single feature to a single prediction). It simplifies the complex decision-making in deep learning that can happen through visualization, including summary and force plots, and explains them to cybersecurity analysts. This enhances trust, facilitates forensic investigation and helps to comply and audit in the secure cloud environment.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the proposed AI framework will be assessed in terms of secure cloud intrusion detection, including the data preprocessing, encrypting, model performance, threat detection, generating alerts, explainable AI, and its comparison with the current models. The balanced UNSW-NB15 dataset is applied in the experiments to show that with the Attention-Enhanced DNN, it is possible to detect cyber threats accurately, reliably, and interpretably and keep the data safe.

A. Experimental setup

The experimental setup was implemented in Python, making use of the deep learning library TensorFlow/ Keras, pre-processing and PCA through the Scikit learn library, and AES 256 encryption with the PyCryptodome library. The UNSW NB15 dataset was ingested, cleaned, encoded, balanced, and normalized then extracted to form features. Role based access and RESTful APIs were used to achieve secure cloud simulation, deep autoencoders, VAEs, and the Attention Enhanced DNN were trained and tested based on accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score parameters. The explainability was added to SHAP, which provides transparency of model decisions. In nutshell, Python offered the complete chain of data processing, security integration, model training, assessment, and explanations.

Fig 3. Class Distribution a) Before Balancing b) After Balancing

In Fig. 3a) the UNSW-NB15 dataset, class distribution prior to the balancing process, with attack traffic (Class 1) having a larger sample size than normal traffic (Class 0), would lead to bias in model learning. Fig. 3b) depicts the distribution following the use of Random Under Sampling (RUS) in which the classes would have equal number of samples to make the training fairer and less biased and enhance reliability and accuracy of intrusion detection.

Fig. 4. a) Original Data Byte Distribution, b) Encrypted Data Byte Distribution

Fig. 4a illustrates the distribution of the value of the bytes of the original data, which is not uniform and has distinct patterns, and thus may be prone to attacks. Figure 4b shows

the distribution following the encryption of AES-256 that the values of the bytes are randomly distributed without patterns after which the information becomes more secure to statistical attacks and cryptographic attacks.

Fig. 5. a) Training vs Validation Accuracy, b) Training vs Validation Loss

In Fig. 5a, the proposed Attention-Enhanced Deep Neural Network obtains progressively increasing and closely matched training and validation accuracy, reaching almost 97%, which is a sign of good generalization and low overfitting. Fig. 5b indicates that the training and validation loss reduces in a gradual but steady way to low values indicating effective optimization, correct regularization and model convergence.

Fig. 6. Threat level distribution

Fig. 7. Alerts vs No alerts

Fig. 8. Confusion matrix

Fig. 9. ROC curve

Fig. 10. Explainable AI based on SHAP

Fig. 11. Comparison of advanced models

The results depicted in Fig. 6-11 all indicate the strength, validity, and usability of the proposed AI-based intrusion detection model in the context of safe cloud and smart computing systems. The distribution of the threat level between Figure 6 shows that the model is highly discriminative with most of the cases being classified as Low (49.4%) and Critical (46.4%) and a minimal number of cases with ambiguous High (2.4%) and Medium (1.8%) categories. Figure 7 also supports the balanced alert-generation mechanism of the framework, which indicates that alerts (49.6%) and non-alerts (50.4%) are distributed almost in similar percentage, which means that probabilistic risk assessment using the ensemble is efficient and does not generate too many false positives, yet its sensitivity is also high. As indicated in the confusion matrix in Figure 8, the accuracy of detection is high with 7,164 attack instances and 7,226 normal instances being correctly identified with very low false positives (174) and false negatives (236), indicating that the instance of attack detection is good as well as the number of false alarms. Figure 9 supports this performance by showing that the AUC of the ROC curve is 0.9971, which means that the classification is almost perfect with high sensitivity and specificity. Figure 10 increases the level of transparency by using explainable AI analysis to demonstrate that some of the latent features (especially Feature 0 and Feature 3) have a significant impact on predictions, confirming the internal logic of decision making by the model. Lastly, Figure 11 compares various models and does confirm that HybridFlowNet and Attention Enhanced DNN are always the best in terms of Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1 score, as hybrid structures and attention mechanisms have a significant positive impact on intrusion detection. On the whole, these findings confirm that the proposed framework is very accurate, balanced, interpretable and effective in high-level cloud-based threat detection.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This research developed a safe and intelligent AI-based cloud and smart computing intrusion detection based on a preprocessing framework, PCA, AES-256 encryption, JWT authentication, deep and variational autoencoders, an Attention-Enhanced Deep Neural Network, ensemble decision-making, probabilistic risk assessment, and SHAP explainability. The system has a high degree of detection accuracy, high level of anomaly detection, low false positives and high degree of interpretability, and it is not compromised on privacy and safe deployment on the cloud. Future directions are to expand to large-scale and multi-cloud settings that are real-time, federated learning, lightweight edge model optimization, and adversarial robustness, adaptive zero-day threat detection, and blockchain based audit and automatic response systems.

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